
IF CONCEPT BOTTLENECKS ARE THE QUESTION, ARE FOUNDATION MODELS THE ANSWER?

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ABSTRACT

Concept Bottleneck Models (CBMs) are neural networks designed to conjoin high performance with *ante-hoc* interpretability. CBMs work by first mapping inputs (e.g., images) to high-level concepts (e.g., visible objects and their properties) and then use these to solve a downstream task (e.g., tagging or scoring an image) in an interpretable manner. Their performance and interpretability, however, *hinge on the quality of the concepts they learn*. The go-to strategy for ensuring good quality concepts is to leverage expert annotations, which are expensive to collect and seldom available in applications. Researchers have recently addressed this issue by introducing “VLM-CBM” architectures that replace manual annotations with weak supervision from foundation models. It is however unclear what is the impact of doing so on the quality of the learned concepts. To answer this question, we put state-of-the-art VLM-CBMs to the test, analyzing their learned concepts empirically using a selection of significant metrics. Our results show that, depending on the task, VLM supervision can sensibly differ from expert annotations, and that concept accuracy and quality are not strongly correlated. Our code is available at <https://github.com/debryu/CQA>.

Keywords Explainable AI, Concept Bottleneck Models, Foundation Models.

1 Introduction

Concept Bottleneck Models (CBMs) [41] are a popular class of neural networks that aim to resolve the traditional trade-off between interpretability and accuracy. In a nutshell, a CBM comprises two learnable modules: a *concept extractor* and an *inference layer*. The former maps the input into an activation vector of high-level concepts, while the latter is generally a white-box model, typically a (sparse) linear layer, that computes predictions from the extracted concepts. For instance, given the image of a red ball, a CBM would encode it into a vector of concept activations – typically logits – for the events (“*shape*” = sphere), (“*color*” = red), and all other combinations established by a pre-defined vocabulary. This vector plays the role of a *bottleneck* encoding interpretable sufficient statistics for the final prediction. CBMs are *explainable-by-design* in the sense that they allow tracing any decision back to the concepts most relevant for it. At the same time, they support representation learning and can achieve high performance for complex data (e.g., images) that are beyond the reach of traditional white-box models. Their modular architecture also brings other benefits, such as support for *correcting* the model’s predictions via user interventions [24, 41, 71, 74] and for

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Figure 1: **A prototypical VLM-CBM.** **Left:** given textual descriptions \mathcal{T} of visual concepts, a VLM is used to annotate a training set \mathcal{D} with per-concept labels or activation scores and (optionally) masks indicating where each concept activates. **Right:** the supervision is typically used to fine-tune a backbone f that extracts concepts from new inputs and a linear layer g for inferring predictions from the concepts. See Section 2 for architecture-specific differences.

debugging the model itself using explanation-based feedback [9, 73]. For these reasons, the same two-step setup has been instantiated into a number of recent classifiers [6, 38, 51, 65, 66, 77] and generative models [21, 34].

It is however possible that the *learned concepts may not match the semantics that humans attribute to them*. The more they deviate, the more opaque the model’s decision process becomes, compromising all benefits that CBMs are designed to provide, including interpretability and intervenability [27, 43, 50, 52, 62].

The go-to strategy for aligning concepts to human semantics is to exploit manual concept annotations, however these are expensive to collect and thus often unavailable in applications. An increasingly prominent solution is to replace manual annotations with *weak supervision* obtained by querying Vision-Language Models (VLMs) with natural language descriptions of the desired concepts [58, 63, 72, 80]. In essence, this procedure distills the concepts learned by a source VLM into a target CBM (cf. Figure 1), with the explicit goal of extending the reach of CBMs to tasks in which no manual annotations are available. The resulting *VLM-CBMs* offer competitive prediction performance and in many cases admit fast inference.³

VLMs, however, may be no silver bullet. In fact, although trained on very large corpora, they can suffer from hallucinations [32], shortcuts [82], and subpar logical [11] and conceptual [64] consistency, and the distillation step risks to pass these defects onto the target CBM. Moreover, even highly accurate concepts can capture spurious contextual information – due to, e.g., *entanglement* [22, 31, 68, 75] and *leakage* [29, 50, 51, 54], illustrated in Figure 2 – in which case the model’s explanations become misleading. Unfortunately, most works on VLM-CBMs are chiefly concerned with downstream accuracy [58, 63, 72, 80, 83] rather than quality of the learned concepts. As a result, it is still unclear whether VLM-CBMs learn concepts of high enough quality.

We fill this gap by directly assessing the concepts learned by representative VLM-CBM architectures – namely, language-in-a-bottle [80], label-free CBMs [58], and vision-language-guided CBMs [72]; see Table 1 for a breakdown of different architectures – using a variety of metrics focusing on diverse, relevant aspects of concept quality. Our experiments on three datasets of increasing complexity indicate that: (i) *VLM concept supervision can sensibly differ from manual annotations*, even when textual descriptions \mathcal{T} of concepts are provided by experts; (ii) in many cases *VLM-CBMs can output correct label predictions by leveraging low-quality concepts* and, more generally, prediction performance and concept quality are not strongly correlated. Overall, our results show that, while VLM-CBMs enjoy wider applicability compared to regular CBMs, *replacing manual with VLM supervision can come at a substantial cost for concept quality*, and thus interpretability. With this work, we hope to prompt more stringent evaluation of concepts learned by state-of-the-art CBMs and to refocus the design of VLM-CBMs on robustness to annotation mistakes and interpretability.

2 The Family of Concept Bottleneck Models

Concept Bottleneck Models (CBMs) [41] combine two neural modules: a *concept extractor* $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$ mapping an input $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$ to a concepts activation vector $\hat{\mathbf{c}} \in \mathbb{R}^k$, which encodes logits of k high-level concepts describing the input; and a *white-box inference layer* $g : \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ mapping the concept activations to a prediction $\hat{y} \in \mathcal{Y}$. Combining f and

³This does not apply to VLM-CBMs that invoke the VLM during inference, see Section 2.

Table 1: **Comparison of CBMs and VLM-CBMs.** The columns which VLM is used, which kind of concept supervision (CONCEPT SUP.) is required, whether the textual concept descriptions (that is, \mathcal{T}) can be supplied externally, and whether the concept extractor requires a pretrained model (PRETRAINED)

MODEL	VLM	CONCEPT SUP.	EXTERNAL \mathcal{T}	PRETRAINED
CBM [41]	–	Labels	✓*	✗**
LaBo [80]	CLIP [60]	Similarity	✓	✓
LF-CBM [58]	CLIP [60]	Similarity	✓	✗
VLG-CBM [72]	G-DINO [47]	Labels, Bboxes	✓	✗
PH-CBM [83]	CLIP [60]	Similarity	✓	✓
DN-CBM [63]	CLIP [60]	Similarity	✗	✓
Naïve	LLaVa [15]	Labels	✓	✗

* The concept vocabulary can be customized in standard CBM too, but this comes at the cost of having to collect manual annotations for any new concepts.

** Some variants of CBMs [19, 42, 66] require using pretrained modules.

g yields the complete predictor. Despite not being restricted to specific data or tasks, CBMs are often used for image classification. This is the use case we focus on.

While the concept extractor is an expressive (but black-box) neural backbone – enabling CBMs to achieve competitive *label* accuracy – the inference layer is white-box. This means that CBMs can naturally explain their own inferences, in that it is easy to identify what concepts contributed the most to each prediction. For instance, if the inference step is implemented – as customary – with a sparse linear layer, then a CBM *explanation* elucidates to what extent each concept activation \hat{c}_j contributes to a prediction \hat{y} by considering the weights $w_{\hat{y},j}$ of the linear layer [37]. See Figure 1 (right) for an example. A major benefit of this setup is *intervenability*: whenever concept are mis-predicted, users can readily replace them with better estimates [12, 24, 41, 71]. It is also possible to teach CBMs to reapply past interventions to unseen instances [74] or to learn when interventions are required at training time [23], thus implementing a form of interactive debugging [76]. CBM architectures differ in how they define, extract and use their concepts, yet popular variants like Concept Embedding Models [84] and GlanceNets [51] all follow the same modular setup. We leave an in-depth discussion of other concept-based models to Section 5.

Learning with expert supervision CBM explanations are interpretable only as long as the concepts are *aligned* with the semantics that humans associate to them [26, 52]. Most CBMs exploit dense concept-level annotations during training to ensure that this is the case. They typically do so by combining two cross-entropy losses, one for the labels $\mathcal{L}_Y = \mathbb{E}_{(\mathbf{x},y)}[-\log p(y | \mathbf{x})]$ and one for the concepts $\mathcal{L}_C = \mathbb{E}_{(\mathbf{x},c)}[-\frac{1}{k} \sum_{j \in [k]} \log p(c_j | \mathbf{x})]$, although the exact formulations vary between architectures [41, 51, 84]. Here, $p(c_j | \mathbf{x}) = \text{sigmoid}(f(\mathbf{x})_j)$ is the predictive distribution of the j -th concept and the expectations run over the training data. The two modules can be trained either independently, sequentially or jointly [41], and the choice can impact the learned representations [50]. Most architectures discussed below follow a sequential setup: the concept extractor is learned first, by minimizing \mathcal{L}_C , and it is then used to train the inference layer via \mathcal{L}_Y . Note also that, in most complex tasks, the concept extractor is pretrained and fine-tuned, rather than trained from scratch.

Learning with VLM supervision A key issue of CBMs is that concept annotations are *not* available in most applications. In these cases, \mathcal{L}_C cannot be used during learning, and weak supervision coming from the label annotations via \mathcal{L}_Y can be insufficient to prevent concepts from deviating, even radically, from the ground-truth ones [10]. In an attempt to widen their applicability, researchers have recently proposed several “VLM-CBMs” that forego expert annotations in favor of a pre-trained Vision-Language Model (VLM). The idea is that, when asked to detect a set of preselected concepts, identified by textual descriptions $\mathcal{T} = \{t_1, \dots, t_k\}$, in any image, a sufficiently large VLM trained on a wealth of diverse data will likely produce a high-quality response. Next, we introduce the key steps involved in learning a VLM-CBM (Figure 1).

Step 1: Obtaining concept supervision from the VLM. A popular option is to obtain concept activations by matching textual concept descriptions and training images in the VLM’s *embedding space*. For instance, Label-free CBMs (LF-CBMs) [58], Language-in-a-Bottle (LaBo) [80] and Post-hoc CBMs (PH-CBM) [83] use CLIP’s visual encoder E_X and text encoder E_T [60] to compute (variants of) the cosine similarity $c_j = \text{sim}(E_X(\mathbf{x}), E_T(t_j))$ between image \mathbf{x} and text t_j .⁴ A more direct route is to collect binary annotations c_j by *prompting* the VLM: one simply feeds a training input \mathbf{x} to the VLM and asks whether a concept described by t_j is present. Vision-Language-Guided CBMs (VLG-CBMs)

⁴We use the same notation for both scores and labels, for simplicity.

[72] do so with Grounding Dino [47]. As a bonus, they also collect per-concept bounding-boxes and use them to filter out low-quality hits. In either case, one obtains similarity scores or binary labels $c \in \mathbb{R}^k$ for each data point.

Finally, Discover-then-Name (DN-CBM) [63] stands out in that it extracts concept activations using sparse autoencoders. Since the extracted concepts are anonymous, they are assigned a name by decoding the image representation to text using CLIP. One downside is that this makes it impossible to prespecify the vocabulary \mathcal{T} .

Step 2: Training the concept extractor with VLM supervision. LF-CBM updates the backbone using a modified concept loss \mathcal{L}_C that regresses on the similarity scores, while VLG-CBM uses the concept annotations to power the cross-entropy loss \mathcal{L}_C . It also optionally augments the training set by adding cut-outs of the input image identified by the concepts’ bounding boxes, so as to encourage learned concepts to be independent of their background. LaBo and PH-CBM are special as they have no backbone⁵ and apply the inference layer directly to the similarity scores.⁶

Step 3: Training the top linear layer. Once the concepts have been learned, the top layer is trained by optimizing \mathcal{L}_Y . The size of concept explanations is kept under control by incorporating a sparsity penalty – such as ℓ_1 -regularization or group lasso [58, 72] – or by normalizing the weights [80].

Issues with VLM-CBMs VLM-CBMs extend the reach of CBMs to tasks that lack dense annotations, yet they are not devoid of risks in that their concepts may not always be high quality. For instance, some concepts learned by popular VLM-CBMs can be irrelevant and/or non-visual (cf. Table 9) and still affect the model’s decision making [72, 80]. The VLMs themselves are likely imperfect. It is well known that CLIP can exhibit erroneous agreements when using cosine similarity [46], and more generally that foundation models are subject to hallucinations [32] and shortcut learning [82]. Ultimately, *it is unclear how VLM-provided supervision affects the learned concepts*. This is precisely what our study aims to find.

The Concept Vocabulary Before proceeding, we briefly mention another important aspect of VLM-CBMs. While most of these models can work with any prespecified vocabulary \mathcal{T} , recent works suggest to generate it automatically by consulting a Large Language Model (LLM), such as ChatGPT [33]. The LLM is simply asked to describe concepts that it deems useful for identifying specific classes [25, 58, 72, 80]. Even filtering out low-quality answers, there is still a chance that invalid concepts may crop up in the vocabulary, as shown in [80] and in A.7.1. Since we aim to assess the impact of VLM-supplied concepts, *we use gold standard annotations as reference*. Therefore, in our experiments we use the corresponding (gold standard) vocabulary for all VLM-CBMs, excluding DN-CBMs in the process as they do not support this mode of operation.

3 Metrics for Concept Quality

We aim to assess to what extent VLM-CBM learn high-quality concepts. Establishing formal conditions for concepts to be deemed interpretable is a difficult open problem [8, 52, 85] and beyond the scope of our paper. We take a different route and ask whether the learned concepts satisfy a minimal set of reasonable desiderata, namely they are accurate (Section 3.1), avoid leakage (Section 3.2), are disentangled (Section 3.3) and avoid unwanted correlations (Section 3.4).

3.1 Accurate Concept Predictions

The most natural requirement is that the learned concepts are *accurate* [41], i.e., that they match their ground-truth values, irrespective of whether they were learned from expert or VLM supervision. Inaccurate concepts can still lead to correct decision-making, but they undermine the credibility of the CBMs’ explanations. For instance, if a VLM-CBM wrongly recognizes the presence of a “*necktie*” and yet uses it to distinguish between male and female celebrities, cf. Fig. 2 (1), it leads to poor explanations of the decision-making. This issue is well known, and indeed, poor concept predictions are the primary target for debugging, which can be done by manually labeling or intervening on concepts for misclassified instances [24, 41, 74].

While most works on VLM-CBMs measure accuracy [58, 63, 72, 80], this is unsuitable for unbalanced concepts (that, e.g., occur rarely) and restricted to binary concepts. However, as mentioned in Section 2, different architectures use different concept supervision, from binary labels (VLG-CBM) to similarity scores (LF-CBM and LaBo). Hence, we assess concept predictions by measuring the Area under the ROC curve, denoted $AUC(C)$, averaged over all concepts in the bottleneck. An additional benefit is that the AUC is robust to unbalanced concept classes, while the accuracy is not.

⁵When viewed as VLM-CBMs, they are in fact equivalent.

⁶The downside is the non-negligible runtime cost of running CLIP at inference time.

Figure 2: **Issues with CBM concepts.** An illustration of the four issues with concept quality and usage affecting CBMs on the CelebA task (cf. Section 4): (1) Attaining high label accuracy does not prevent learning *inaccurate concepts*. (2) CBMs can maximize label performance by learning *leaky concepts* that include irrelevant contextual cues. (3) *Entangled concepts* encode unwanted information about one another, affecting out-of-distribution behavior. (4) *Impure concepts* encode unwanted correlations that do not exist among ground-truth concepts.

3.2 Avoiding Concept Leakage

High concept accuracy is not sufficient to ensure that the concepts possess human-aligned semantics. Prior work has shown that (even accurate) concepts can suffer from *leakage*⁷, i.e., they may unintentionally carry information that helps with label predictions but is semantically incongruent with the concept itself [29, 49–51, 54]. For instance, in Fig. 2 (2) the model maximizes the score of the correct (“male”) class by encoding the name of a basketball team within the concept “young”.

Unfortunately, leakage does not directly impact model performance, and as such it can be difficult to detect. Prior works [29, 49–51] suggest to measure the retained amount of label accuracy when restricting the bottleneck to concepts that are known to be *irrelevant* for the prediction task. In order to measure the overall leakage present in the whole bottleneck, we extend this idea as follows. First, we sort all concepts by their *ground-truth* Pearson correlation with the task label y , least correlated first. Second, we train two linear SVMs [16] to predict the ground-truth label y from the first ℓ concepts, one feeding on the ground-truth concept labels \mathbf{c} and the other on the predicted concepts $\hat{\mathbf{c}}$, and measure the gap in their F_1 -scores, i.e., $\text{gap}_\ell = F_1^{CBM}(Y; \ell) - F_1^{GT}(Y; \ell)$. Intuitively, a linear classifier predicting the label from the first ℓ (i.e., least correlated) concepts should perform very poorly if $\ell \ll k$; however, *this is not the case if they leak information (about the label) encoded by remaining, most correlated ones*. We repeat this step for $\ell = 1, \dots, k$ and then record the average of all gaps:

$$\text{LEAK} = \frac{1}{k \cdot Z} \sum_{\ell=1}^k \max(\text{gap}_\ell, 0) \quad (1)$$

Here, $Z = 1 - \sum_{\ell=1}^k F_1^{GT}(Y; \ell)/k$ is a normalizing constant that ensures LEAK has a maximum value equal to 1. LEAK is zero if and only if all performance gaps are equal to or less than zero, i.e., the learned concepts provide the same or less information about the label as the ground-truth ones. Vice versa, a value close to 1 indicates that the learned concepts leak task-relevant information. The pseudo-code for its evaluation is confined in Section A.3.

3.3 Disentanglement of Concepts

Leakage occurs when concepts unintentionally encode spurious task-relevant information. In some cases, this happens because they encode information about one another, as doing so can improve label accuracy. Therefore, a key requirement is that learned concepts are *disentangled* [36, 52], i.e., manipulating the input to alter one concept should

⁷We are interested in leakage as it can be detrimental to interpretability [50], however it is still not clear if it should be avoided at all costs. For instance, in some settings, leakage has been shown to improve the robustness of the model to interventions at the test time [23].

not affect the prediction of the others [75]. E.g., in Fig. 2 (3) the presence of “bang” is entangled with the “hair color”. Concepts that mix irrelevant factors are problematic as they do not match the semantics of their ground-truth counterpart, complicating interpretation [52]. For example, if the concept “bang” contains information about the “hair color”, it can behave unpredictably when this is switched on or off in the data [56]. Disentanglement is also a prerequisite for concept reuse, generalization, and supporting post-hoc alignment with users [10, 26].

We measure disentanglement with DCI, a popular metric that estimates the inter-relations between predicted and ground-truth concepts [22]. It does so by training a non-linear model, e.g., a random forest, predicting the ground-truth concepts from the learned ones and then computing relevance scores R_{ij} that reflect how predictive the i -th learned concept is for the j -th ground-truth concept. The DCI disentanglement score D_i for the concept c_i is then defined as:

$$D_i := 1 - \left(- \sum_{j=1}^k P_{ij} \log_k P_{ij} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $P_{ij} = R_{ij} / \sum_{\ell} R_{i\ell}$. The degree of disentanglement of the model is then given by computing a weighted average of all disentanglement scores, see Section A.5. DIS has a maximum score of 1 and occurs when concepts are completely disentangled; instead, the score is 0 (worst case) if learned concepts equally depend on all ground-truth ones.

3.4 Unwanted Correlations among Concepts

Disentanglement, as measured with DCI, decreases with the degree to which learned concepts contain information about other concepts.

Nonetheless, in practice, learned concepts can be naturally correlated [85], due to sampling bias of the data. For example, the concept “bald” is likely to be correlated with the presence of “beard”, so a model may capture these correlations. However, if correlation among learned concepts exceeds the one in the data, the CBM may incur situations where “beard” is predicted because of the absence of hair, as portrayed in Fig. 2 (4).

The Oracle Impurity Score (OIS) [85] measures this “impurity” by penalizing whether unwanted correlations appear among the learned concepts. It does so by comparing the inter concept relations among ground-truth concepts with the inter concept relations among learned ones. Similar to DCI, a non-linear model, e.g., a random forest, is trained to predict the same ground-truth concepts from ground-truth concepts, obtaining a relevance matrix $R_{ij}^{(gt)}$. The same procedure is done by training a model from the same family to predict the ground-truth concepts from the model ones. This results to the same relevance matrix R_{ij} accounted in DCI.

The divergence between these two matrices serves as an impurity metric, quantifying the amount of undesired information in the learned concepts:

$$\text{OIS} = \frac{2}{k} \sum_{ij=1}^k |R_{ij} - R_{ij}^{(gt)}|^2 \quad (3)$$

An OIS of 1 indicates a complete misalignment between ground-truth and learned concepts, i.e., the i -th concept representation can predict one or many other concepts, except the ones it supposed even when the concepts are independent, while an OIS of 0 denotes perfect alignment, meaning that the i -th learned concept does not capture any unwanted correlation.

Relationships between Metrics We point out that some of these metrics are partly correlated. While concept accuracy is not a strong indicator of concept quality – in the sense that even if it is perfect this does not rule out leakage [50, 54], entanglement [29, 51], or impure correlations [85] – the amount of leakage does partly depend on whether concepts are entangled, and partly on whether they capture non-conceptual stylistic information [52].⁸ In practice, especially in difficult classification tasks, the concept extractor may optimize for accuracy by exploiting wrongly correlated, entangled, or leaky concepts, precisely because doing so maximizes the amount of task-relevant information in the bottleneck [86]. Still, we empirically evaluate all four metrics so as to provide a fuller picture of VLM-CBMs concepts.

4 Empirical Analysis

We tackle empirically the following research questions:

Q1 Are expert and VLMs annotations comparable?

⁸Specifically, concepts that are both disentangled and independent from style entail no leakage, but the converse may not hold: if a concept c_i is *non-linearly* entangled into another c_j (according to Eq. (2)), a *linear* layer may be unable to extract useful information carried about the label by c_i from c_j , thereby leading to zero leakage.

Q2 Are high label accuracy and high concept accuracy correlated in VLM-CBMs?

Q3 Are VLM-CBM concepts of high-quality?

Data sets We consider three concept-annotated data sets for image classification. Shapes3d [39] is a synthetic data set of renderings of 3d objects with varying shape, color, orientation and background, for a total of 42 different binary concepts. The ground-truth binary label $y \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether a specific object (a *red pill*) is present in the image. In total, we use 48k samples for training, 5k for validation, and 30k for testing. CelebA [48] contains about 200k images (of size $178 \times 218 \times 3$) of celebrity faces and provides manual annotations for 40 binary concepts (hair color, presence of glasses, whether the person is smiling, *etc.*). The model is asked to predict the “gender” of the celebrity from the remaining 39 concepts. We selected 25k examples for training, 5k for validation, and 20k for testing. CUB [78] is a bird classification task spanning 200 different classes and 112 concepts (bill shape, body color, feather pattern, *etc.*). It consists of 4.8k images for training, 1.2k for validation, and 5.8k for testing.

Architectures We evaluate three representative VLM-CBMs, namely LaBo [80], LF-CBM [58], and VLG-CBM [72]. As baselines, we consider a standard CBM [41] and Naïve, a CBM trained on concept labels gathered from a recent VLM balancing performance and efficiency. Specifically, Naïve first queries LLaVA-Phi3 [15], for each training image, about whether each concept in \mathcal{T} is present or not, and then fits a sparse linear layer on the resulting binary answers with a cross-entropy loss; see [Section A.2](#) for further details.

For all models except LaBo, which has no backbone, we implement the image encoder using CLIP [60] (ViT-B16 and RN50 versions) or ResNet-18[30] in both Shapes3d and CelebA (the former for LF-CBM and VLG-CBM, the latter for CBM and Naïve). Following [58, 72], in CUB we use a ResNet-18 version pre-trained on CUB instead. As we will show, this seemingly innocuous choice noticeably affects both label and concept quality. In all cases, we implement the inference layer as a linear layer feeding on concept logits. Following the original implementations, LF-CBM and VLG-CBM incentivize sparsity by using GLM-SAGA [79], while CBM and Naïve minimize the unregularized cross entropy loss and LaBo regularizes the linear layer by applying a softmax operator to the weight rows [80]. All details regarding architectures and hyperparameter tuning are reported in [Sections A.1](#) and [A.4](#).

Concept vocabularies All VLM-CBMs allow generating a task-specific concept vocabulary by querying an LLM (see [Section 2](#)). This procedure may yield invalid concepts [72] and more generally complicates comparing against gold-standard concept annotations. To ensure a fair evaluation, in each dataset we fix the same vocabulary \mathcal{T} for all competitors. The complete list of concept descriptions for each dataset can be found in [Section A.7.2](#).

4.1 Q1: VLMs supervision does not match expert annotation

We begin by assessing the quality of the VLM annotations. To this end, we measure the macro precision and recall of the VLM annotations with respect to the gold standard annotations for all concepts in the vocabulary and report their average over the training examples in [Table 2](#). Overall, *annotation quality differs substantially across VLMs and data sets*. The best annotations are obtained on CUB (112 concepts), with most VLMs achieving at least 53% precision and 58% recall – in fact, G-DINO attains high precision and recall above 90% and LLaVa 92% precision above and medium recall (about 66%). VLM annotations in CelebA (39 concepts) are noticeably worse – the best option being LLaVa, with precision and recall above 67% – and very poor in Shapes3d (42 concepts): CLIP, the best VLM, achieves precision and recall barely above 30% and suffers from high variance.

We hypothesize that annotation quality depends on a combination of factors: (i) Whether the VLM has encountered concepts closely matching the queried textual description during training (e.g., hair colors, eyeglasses).⁹ (ii) Whether the input is in-distribution. E.g., VLMs may struggle to annotate Shapes3d precisely because its synthetic images fall out-of-distribution. It is in fact unlikely that VLMs would have trouble identifying concepts such as colors or shapes that likely appear in their training data. While bigger VLM, such as Llama-vision 3.2 [28], might yield better annotations, they are not typically used for VLM-CBMs as they substantially increase computational costs. We leave a more detailed study thereof to future work, while we provide few examples of automated annotations in [Fig. 5](#). More details on the experiment can be found in [Section A.6](#).

4.2 Q2: VLM-CBMs output good labels but low-quality concepts

Next, we evaluate VLM-CBMs predictions and concepts proper using F_1 score for the former (denoted $F_1(Y)$) and $AUC(C)$ for the latter ([Section 3.1](#)). The results for all models and data sets are reported in [Table 3](#).

⁹We remark that understanding under what conditions enable VLMs to acquire high-quality concepts is still an open problem [61].

Table 2: Agreement between ground-truth and VLMs annotations in terms of (macro) precision and recall, averaged across all concepts and examples.

	Shapes3d		CelebA		CUB200	
	MPr (\uparrow)	MRc (\uparrow)	MPr (\uparrow)	MRc (\uparrow)	MPr (\uparrow)	MRc (\uparrow)
CLIP	0.32 \pm 0.23	0.30 \pm 0.23	0.58 \pm 0.08	0.65 \pm 0.08	0.53 \pm 0.04	0.58 \pm 0.04
G-DINO	0.18 \pm 0.07	0.64 \pm 0.07	0.56 \pm 0.11	0.54 \pm 0.11	0.97 \pm 0.07	0.90 \pm 0.07
LLaVa	0.13 \pm 0.06	0.13 \pm 0.06	0.69 \pm 0.13	0.67 \pm 0.13	0.92 \pm 0.08	0.66 \pm 0.08

Table 3: Results averaged over 5 runs. Best results are in **bold** and second best are underlined.

	MODEL	$F_1(Y)$ (\uparrow)	AUC(C) (\uparrow)	LEAK (\downarrow)	DIS (\uparrow)	OIS (\downarrow)
Shapes3d	CBM	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.18 \pm 0.06	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.08 \pm 0.01
	Naïve	0.54 \pm 0.06	0.17 \pm 0.01	<u>0.14</u> \pm 0.01	0.20 \pm 0.01	0.16 \pm 0.01
	LaBo	0.76 \pm 0.01	<u>0.31</u> \pm 0.01	0.81 \pm 0.01	0.28 \pm 0.01	0.15 \pm 0.01
	LF-CBM	<u>0.96</u> \pm 0.01	<u>0.31</u> \pm 0.01	0.64 \pm 0.01	<u>0.28</u> \pm 0.01	<u>0.15</u> \pm 0.01
	VLG-CBM	0.52 \pm 0.01	0.24 \pm 0.01	0.06 \pm 0.10	0.24 \pm 0.01	0.16 \pm 0.01
	CelebA	CBM	0.95 \pm 0.01	0.75 \pm 0.01	0.41 \pm 0.01	0.74 \pm 0.01
Naïve	0.95 \pm 0.01	<u>0.51</u> \pm 0.01	0.99 \pm 0.01	<u>0.39</u> \pm 0.01	<u>0.16</u> \pm 0.01	
LaBo	0.97 \pm 0.01	0.38 \pm 0.01	<u>0.42</u> \pm 0.01	0.28 \pm 0.01	0.18 \pm 0.01	
LF-CBM	0.99 \pm 0.01	0.41 \pm 0.01	0.53 \pm 0.01	0.29 \pm 0.01	0.17 \pm 0.01	
VLG-CBM	<u>0.98</u> \pm 0.01	0.32 \pm 0.01	0.92 \pm 0.01	0.21 \pm 0.01	0.20 \pm 0.01	
CUB	CBM	0.69 \pm 0.01	0.91 \pm 0.01	0.10 \pm 0.02	0.75 \pm 0.01	0.09 \pm 0.01
Naïve	0.66 \pm 0.01	0.43 \pm 0.03	<u>0.02</u> \pm 0.01	0.27 \pm 0.02	0.15 \pm 0.01	
LaBo	0.27 \pm 0.01	0.25 \pm 0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.18 \pm 0.01	0.15 \pm 0.01	
LF-CBM	<u>0.68</u> \pm 0.01	0.25 \pm 0.01	0.01 \pm 0.01	0.19 \pm 0.01	0.16 \pm 0.01	
VLG-CBM	0.60 \pm 0.01	<u>0.79</u> \pm 0.01	<u>0.02</u> \pm 0.01	<u>0.60</u> \pm 0.01	<u>0.10</u> \pm 0.01	

A first key finding is that VLM-CBMs *often achieve $F_1(Y)$ comparable to the CBM baseline using substantially less accurate concepts*, as indicated by AUC(C).¹⁰ The gap is particularly noticeable in Shapes3d, where all VLM-CBMs have much lower AUC(C) than CBM, yet LF-CBM (and to a lesser extent LaBo) surprisingly achieve good F_1 . On the other hand, Naïve and VLG-CBM produce label predictions that look almost random, showing that the learned concepts carry very little to no information about the label. The other two data sets paint a similar picture: in CelebA, AUC(C) never crosses 50% while $F_1(Y)$ for all models is always above 95%, matching or even surpassing the CBM baseline; and in CUB, the VLM-CBMs fare poorly at AUC(C)–the only exception being VLG-CBM, with AUC(C) = 79% – but all of them except LaBo achieve competitive $F_1(Y)$ ($\geq 60\%$, close the CBM’s 69%). Again, this suggests a disconnect between label and concept accuracy, and that *maximizing the former provides no guarantees about the latter* [10].

We readily acknowledge that for LF-CBM, LaBo, and VLG-CBM, our $F_1(Y)$ results on CUB are lower than those reported in the original publications [58, 72, 80]. This is because the original evaluation used a broad set of LLM-generated concepts whose number can be up to ten thousand (a comparison of bottleneck sizes on CUB dataset can be found in Table 10). In contrast, *we always employ the gold-standard concept vocabulary*. Note that this is sufficient for inferring the correct labels, and indeed the associated manual concept annotations enable CBM to perform well on all data sets in terms of $F_1(Y)$. Our results indicate that *restricting these models to the gold-standard vocabulary does affect label accuracy compared to using larger vocabularies*. When contrasted with existing results, this leads us to hypothesize that a more extensive concept vocabulary allows the bottleneck to retain more information about label predictions even if concepts do not correspond to anything meaningful [72] or they are randomly generated [50].

Finally, we attribute the lackluster performance of LaBo to the fact that it is the only model without a backbone pretrained on CUB. We believe such task-specific pre-training, which is common practice for this data set [58, 72], brings a substantial performance advantage and as such it should be employed whenever feasible.

4.3 Q3: VLM-CBMs often leverage poor quality concepts

We now turn to evaluating specific aspects of concept quality, beginning with leakage (Section 3.2). Compatibly with existing findings [29, 50, 51, 54], the results in Table 3 indicate that *CBM is affected by leakage in all datasets*, with a maximum of 41% in CelebA and a minimum of 10% in CUB. In Shapes3d, both CLIP-based models (LF-CBM and

¹⁰The poor concept accuracy is likely due to poor VLM annotations, see Section 4.1.

Figure 3: **Gaps of the concept leakage test in CelebA and CUB.** The higher the gap, the more the subset of learned concepts leaks information for label prediction. (Left) Gaps on CelebA upon varying the subset of concepts from 1 to 39. All model concepts always display a non-negative gain in label F_1 compared to ground-truth concepts. (Right) Gaps on CUB upon varying the subset of concepts from 1 to 112. Only CBM is affected by leakage when considering smaller subsets of concepts.

LaBo) are affected by leakage. VLG-CBM is the only method that sensibly avoids leakage in this dataset, despite faring poorly in label predictions. Note that a low $F_1(Y)$ does not imply leakage is absent, as demonstrated by the results of Naive.¹¹

The trend is flipped in CelebA: LaBo fares similarly to CBM, LF-CBM drops by 11%, Naive attains maximum leakage despite achieving an $AUC(C)$ higher than other VLM-CBMs, and VLG-CBM is highly affected by it, with 92% leakage. In Fig. 3 (left), we report the gaps for CelebA, which better spot on which subset of concepts (VLM) CBMs suffer leakage more. For example, the plots show that even if CBM and LaBo have similar LEAK (41% vs 42%), they display different behavior: LaBo displays a small amount of leakage in every concept, while CBM reveals that only a few concepts are more leaky. In particular, the concepts “big lips” and “bald” appear to introduce the most substantial amount of leakage on CBM. Interestingly, we observe that gaps of all models are above zero when considering all concepts in the bottleneck.¹² The evaluation on CUB portrays a different picture where only CBM and Naive are sensibly affected by leakage. The high gaps for CBM in Fig. 3 (right) show that a big proportion of label information is spread onto few concepts. VLG-CBM and LaBo instead do not leak label information in the concepts, as visible for the always small or negative gaps.

Finally, we look at disentanglement and oracle impurity score (Sections 3.3 and 3.4). Overall, for all tested models, disentanglement is positively correlated with $AUC(C)$ while OIS is negative correlated with it. In all datasets, CBM attain the highest DIS and the lowest OIS thanks to expert annotation, whereas VLM-CBMs fare below the baseline Naive in Shapes3d and CelebA. On CUB, VLG-CBM achieve higher DIS and lower OIS compared to other models, thanks to the higher quality of annotation of G-DINO. We analyze the DCI importance matrices R_{ij} for CelebA on a single, optimal $F_1(Y)$ run of each competitor, cf. Fig. 7. All VLM-CBMs drastically deviates from the behavior of CBM, showing different entangled concepts based on the VLM they leverage. For example, Naive displays high entanglement for the concept “goatee” and “wearing lipstick”, CLIP-based approaches show that “goatee”, “no beard”, and “smiling” are the most entangled concepts, whereas VLG-CBM entangles several concepts, the most evident being “gray hair”, and “pale skin”.

5 Related Work

Concept-based models are a heterogeneous class of models that leverage learned concepts to glue together low-level perception with transparent high-level reasoning, see [35, 59, 70] for recent overviews. *Unsupervised* models rely on

¹¹This can be noted from the plot on gaps in Fig. 4, where Naive leaks a small amount of label information at early stages with a subset of a few irrelevant concepts. The gaps reduce at later stages, especially when adding all concepts, where, eventually, Naive can no longer achieve label F_1 above the ground-truth.

¹²This shows that *extra, stylistic information* about labels is encoded in the bottleneck beyond the predefined ground-truth concepts. For example, as in Fig. 2 (2), the model could exploit textual information within the image (that is correlated to the label) to improve the prediction.

concept discovery techniques, and foster interpretability via penalty terms architectural biases, such as *sparsity* [2], *orthogonality* [14], *reconstruction* [45] and *prototypes* [13]. Supervised CBMs differ in what information they encode in the concept bottleneck: *concept activations* [41], *embeddings* [84], *probabilities* [38, 51, 77], or *discrete activations* [29, 49]. VLM-CBMs relax the need for expert supervision by leveraging pre-trained VLMs.

The issue of interpretability in CBMs is well-known. Surprisingly, most works on VLM-CBMs do not focus on *concept quality* [58, 63, 69, 72, 80]. It is well-known that, however, the semantics of concepts learned from data can be misleading [27] and that even achieving high concept accuracy is not sufficient to ensure concepts are interpretable [8, 29, 50, 51, 54]. A number of metrics have been introduced to establish desirable properties of learned concepts. We focus on *leakage* [29, 50], *disentanglement* [51], *oracle impurity score* [85], but other works have looked at *completeness* [29, 81], *locality* [62], or *post-hoc alignment* [10, 55]. Techniques for improving concept quality build on causal insights [4] and on side-information [29, 65] obtained from either experts [9, 44, 73, 76] or foundation models [72]. Provided that the extracted concepts are high-quality, the *classifier must also be high-quality* to guarantee interpretable decision making. Several works have indicated that *sparsity* is a central property [2, 5, 58] and that can lead to least leakage of information [72], while other works focus on making the classifier decision mechanism more *understandable* by learning logic rules as in decision trees [6, 7], or *verifiable* [18], or *causally transparent* [17, 20, 57]. Since we focus specifically on concept quality, we leave to future work to examine how VLM-CBMs stimulate classifier quality.

Beyond CBMs. The issue of concept quality extends beyond CBMs to other branches of AI, including Neuro-Symbolic AI and Foundation Models. For instance, it was shown that the concepts learned by Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy) architectures can be compromised by shortcuts [53], and these findings were recently extended to CBMs [10]. A popular solution is, just like for CBMs, to leverage foundation models [74]. Our work highlights that this strategy comes with its own set of pitfalls and cannot strictly guarantee the trustworthiness of the predictor.

6 Conclusion

Our results suggest that, despite significantly broadening the applicability of CBMs, VLMs are unfortunately not yet an accurate substitute for high-quality expert annotations. Annotation quality translates not only to worse concept accuracy, but it also results in higher leakage, worse entanglement, and more impure concepts, depending on the dataset. While it remains to be seen whether the quality of machine-generated concepts could match man-made ones, our results highlight that leakage remains an open problem even when using predefined (and sufficient) textual description of concepts. In turn, this means that VLM-CBMs tend to be less interpretable than CBMs, at least in applications where a direct comparison with expert annotations is feasible.

With this work, we hope to help understand potential limitations of VLM-CBMs and to prompt researchers to place more emphasis on concept quality when developing future architectures. We will conclude by pointing out possible ways forward. One natural solution is, of course, to simply wait for VLMs to improve. While this is not unlikely given recent trends, leveraging bigger models necessarily comes at a substantial computational cost. We suggest that a more future-proof strategy, not necessarily orthogonal to the former, is to design VLM-CBMs that are more robust to low-quality concept annotations. This could be achieved, for instance, by leveraging sound confidence estimates of the VLM’s annotations during training [1], exploiting well-known regularization terms and learning strategies which proved effective for regular CBMs [4, 26, 51], and actively seeking manual annotations for low-quality concepts [24, 74].

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Declarations

The authors declare no competing interest.

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Appendix A Experimental Details

All experiments were implemented using Python 3 and Pytorch [3]. The code is available at <https://github.com/debryu/CQA>.

A.1 Architectures

We list here the description of all architectures used in our experiments, where, for ease of reading, we omit the details about the backbones we used. For each component we specify its name, input, output, what it produces (i.e. the output of a layer could simply be an intermediate process, and if so the field is empty, or return important information such as logits or probabilities) and lastly if the layer/component is frozen or being trained. We also specify how a particular component is trained, where the options are:

1. XENT: standard PyTorch cross entropy loss computed between ground-truth and predicted values.
2. SVM: we use Support Vector Machine [67] (specifically the scikit learn [implementation](#)) to fit a linear classifier.
3. GLM-SAGA: we minimize an elastic net loss using the GLM-SAGA solver created by [79], in order to obtain a sparse linear classifier.

Table 4: CBM architecture.

Input	Type	Output	Produces	Trained	with
(224, 224, 3)	ResNet18	(1000)		✓	
(1000)	Linear	(#Conc.)	Concept Logits	✓	XENT
(#Conc.)	Sigmoid	(#Conc.)	Concept Probs	✗	
(#Conc.)	Linear	(#Class)	Class Logits	✓	GLM-SAGA

Table 5: LaBo architecture.

Input	Type	Output	Produces	Trained	with
(224, 224, 3)	CLIP ViT-B/16	(768)		✗	
(768), (768, #Conc.) ¹³	Dot Product	(#Conc.)		✗	
(#Conc.)	Normalization	(#Conc.)	Concept Logits	✗	
(#Conc.)	Linear	(#Class)	Class Logits	✓	XENT

Table 6: Naïve architecture.

Input	Type	Output	Produces	Trained	with
(224, 224, 3)	ResNet18	(1000)		✓	
(1000)	Linear	(#Conc.)	Concept Logits	✓	XENT
(#Conc.)	Sigmoid	(#Conc.)	Concept Probs	✗	
(#Conc.)	Linear	(#Class)	Class Logits	✓	SVM

Table 7: LF-CBM architecture.

Input	Type	Output	Produces	Trained	with
(224, 224, 3)	CLIP ViT-B/16	(768)		✗	
(768)	Linear	(#Conc.)	Concept Logits	✓	XENT
(#Conc.)	Linear	(#Class)	Class Logits	✓	GLM-SAGA

For CUB, the ResNet18 output shape is 200, matching the number of classes, and so the following linear layer will have input of dimension 200 while keeping unvaried the other components of the architecture.

Pre-trained models are downloaded from [PyTorch](#) and [imgclsmb](#).

¹³(768) is the CLIP image embedding, while (768, #Conc.) are the textual concepts encoded using CLIP.

Table 8: VLG-CBM architecture.

Input	Type	Output	Produces	Trained	with
(224, 224, 3)	CLIP ViT-B/16	(768)		\times	
(768)	Linear	(#Conc.)		\checkmark	XENT
(#Conc.)	Normalization	(#Conc.)	Concept Logits	\times	
(#Conc.)	Linear	(#Class)	Class Logits	\checkmark	GLM-SAGA

A.2 Naïve

We consider a fixed concept dictionary \mathcal{T} consisting of a total of k concept textual descriptions. According to the description of VLM-CBMs training [Section A.1](#), our proposed baselines consist of the following three steps:

1. Gathering concept annotation for all input-output pairs from the training set by querying a LLaVa model to provide a binary label if any of the concepts in \mathcal{T} is present.
2. We use the collected binary concept annotation to train the concept extractor f .
3. By freezing the concept extractor, a linear layer g is trained to predict the classes from concept activations.

To execute the first step, similarly to [\[72\]](#), we prompt the VLM with the following script:

```
"This is an image of {class_name}.
Does the image contain {prefix}{obj}{suffix}?
Please reply only with 'Yes' or 'No'."
```

where `class_name` is the class associated to the input sample and `obj` is the concept being queried. To adapt to different datasets, we added `prefix` and `suffix`, which can be empty strings or customized to enrich the prompt. For example, in CelebA we use the prefix *"a person with"*, so that the full prompt ends up being "Does the image contain {a person with} {Moustache}?".

When the model does not follow the prompt with its answer, we append after the response

```
"Given this information, my 'Yes' or 'No' answer is:"
```

If the response from the model is still not satisfactory, we set the concept annotation value to 0. The VLM is run locally, using [ollama](#).

A.3 Leakage Calculation

To establish each concept's relevance to label prediction, we compute the Pearson correlation coefficient between each ground-truth concept and the label. Then, both ground-truth and predicted concepts are sorted by increasing correlation with the label, so that highly correlated concepts are placed last. Next, we use the iterative algorithm in [Algorithm 1](#) to implement the procedure detailed in [Section 3.2](#).

A.4 Hyperparameter selection

During training, we apply early stopping when a model's validation loss does not decrease after 16 consecutive epochs.

We conducted a grid search over different sets of hyperparameters and determined the best combination by monitoring the label F_1 score on the validation set with wandb. As for the optimizer, we used Adam [\[40\]](#). Besides more common hyperparameters, we use a flag `unfreeze` to control the number of layers to unfreeze from the ResNet backbone (starting from the last one). The flag `balanced` is used to handle dataset imbalances when training the concept bottleneck.

CBM **model parameters** are set as: `-epochs=20, -unfreeze=5, -lr=0.001, -batch_size=512, -backbone=resnet18, -optimizer=adamw, -balanced`.

Naïve **model parameters** are set as: `-epochs=20, -unfreeze=5, -lr=0.001, -predictor=svm, -c_svm=1, -batch_size=512, -backbone=resnet18, -optimizer=adamw, -balanced, -ollama_model=llava-phi3`.

LaBo **model parameters** are set as: `-lr=0.01, -batch_size=258, -backbone=clip_RN50, -feature_layer=layer4, -clip_name=ViT-B/16`.

Algorithm 1 Compute F1 Gap Between Predicted and Ground-Truth Concepts

```

1: gaps = []
2: for  $i = 1$  to  $k$  do
3:    $\hat{C}_{train} \leftarrow$  predicted concepts on train set
4:    $\hat{C}_{test} \leftarrow$  predicted concepts on test set
5:   SVM.train( $\hat{C}_{train}[1 : i], y_{train}$ )
6:   predictions  $\leftarrow$  SVM.predict( $\hat{C}_{test}[1 : i]$ )
7:   F1_predicted  $\leftarrow$  compute_F1(predictions,  $y_{test}$ )
8:    $C_{train} \leftarrow$  ground truth concepts on train set
9:    $C_{test} \leftarrow$  ground truth concepts on test set
10:  SVM.train( $C_{train}[1 : i], y_{train}$ )
11:  predictions  $\leftarrow$  SVM.predict( $C_{test}[1 : i]$ )
12:  F1_ground_truth  $\leftarrow$  compute_F1(predictions,  $y_{test}$ )
13:  gaps.append( $F1\_predicted - F1\_ground\_truth$ )
14: end for
15: return: gaps

```

▷ List of F_1 gaps for each step

LF-CBM **model parameters** are set as: `-lr=0.01, -batch_size=258, -backbone=clip_RN50, -feature_layer=layer4, -clip_name=ViT-B/16, -proj_steps=1000, clip_cutoff=0.0, -interpretability_cutoff=0.0`.¹⁴

VLG-CBM **model parameters** are set as: `-backbone=clip_RN50, -feature_layer=layer4, -crop_to_concept_prob=0.01, -cbl_confidence_threshold=0.15, -cbl_hidden_layers=3, -cbl_epochs=8, -cbl_lr=0.001, -val_split=0.1`.

For the models that require GLM-SAGA [79] we use the following parameters: `-glm_alpha=0.99, -glm_step_size=0.1, -n_iters=2000, -lam=0.0007, -saga_batch_size=256`.

Lastly, when running experiments on CUB we use `-backbone=resnet18_cub` for CBM, Naïve, LF-CBM and VLG-CBM. For LF-CBM and VLG-CBM we also specify `-feature_layer=features.final_pool` which is the last layer of the pre-trained ResNet backbone. All the other hyperparameters are kept the same, except for VLG-CBM **parameters** which are: `-backbone=resnet18_cub, -feature_layer=features.final_pool, -crop_to_concept_prob=0.1, -cbl_confidence_threshold=0.15, -cbl_hidden_layers=0, -cbl_epochs=35, -cbl_lr=0.0005, -lam=0.0002`.

¹⁴The last two hyperparameters are set to zero to prevent unwanted concept filtering.

A.5 DCI framework

The disentanglement metric is defined as the weighted average over all disentanglement scores D_i appearing in Eq. (2), where $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$:

$$D = \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_i D_i, \quad \text{where } \rho_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N R_{ij}}{\sum_{\ell=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^K R_{\ell j}} \quad (4)$$

A.6 Evaluating VLM annotations

To evaluate VLM annotations we use macro average precision and recall measured on predicted concepts versus ground-truth ones. While G-DINO and Naïve produce boolean annotations (i.e. a concept is either 0 or 1), this is not true for CLIP embeddings. To overcome this, we train a logistic regressor model for each concept (using CLIP embeddings as input), and then assign 0 or 1 to the concept based on the output of that model.

We also take into consideration whether some concepts are mutually exclusive, such as in Shapes3d where concept 1 through 10 are the one-hot encoding of the color, so only one will be active. With that in mind, when evaluating CLIP annotations on Shapes3d we evaluate concept activation separately for each group of concepts (wall color, background color, object color, size and shape), setting as *active* only the concept with highest activation withing the group.

A.7 Concept Vocabulary

A.7.1 Concept set generation

When the concept vocabulary is not available, a common choice is to query a Large Language Model to create a set of textual descriptions of the concepts \mathcal{T} . However, one known limitation is that an LLM can produce invalid concepts [80]. In general, a high-quality concept vocabulary generation is difficult because the concept names need to avoid being overly specific or narrow for the task. In Table 9, we report some examples of invalid concepts in the generated vocabularies for CUB. These concept descriptions are taken from the original evaluation of the methods we tested.

Table 9: Examples of invalid concepts from the CUB vocabulary generated using LLMs. The concepts are taken from the filtered set of the original implementation [58, 72, 80].

Method	Generated Concepts	
	Irrelevant	Non-visual
LF-CBM [58]	"a Mohs hardness of 10"	"loud, rasping voice" "a loud, harsh cry" "a loud, high-pitched song"
LaBo [80]	"hollow trees or stumps" "adds color and life to our forests" "named after anna mary robertson, better known as grandma moses"	"series of high, piping notes" "song is a trill" "cawing can be quite loud and annoying"
VLG-CBM [72]	"a trackpad or mouse"	"a loud, melodious song" "loud, rasping voice" "a loud caw"

A.7.2 Fixed Concept Set

Our objective is to use a vocabulary of concepts that can be shared across different models, which also includes access to ground-truth values. With that in mind, we took the textual description of the ground-truth concepts, with some minor preprocessing such as removing underscores for better understanding. We list below the complete sets of concepts used in our experiments for the CUB, Ce1ebA, and Shapes3d datasets.

CUB concept set

dagger beak	white back	yellow forehead	multi-colored back
hooked seabird beak	buff back	black forehead	solid tail
all-purpose beak	notched tail	white forehead	striped tail
cone beak	brown upper-tail	brown under-tail	multi-colored tail
brown wing	grey upper-tail	grey under-tail	solid belly
grey wing	black upper-tail	black under-tail	brown primary color
yellow wing	white upper-tail	white under-tail	grey primary color
black wing	buff upper-tail	buff under-tail	yellow primary color
white wing	eyebrow head	brown nape	black primary color
buff wing	plain head	grey nape	white primary color
brown upperparts	brown breast	yellow nape	buff primary color
grey upperparts	grey breast	black nape	grey leg
yellow upperparts	yellow breast	white nape	black leg
black upperparts	black breast	buff nape	buff leg
white upperparts	white breast	brown belly	grey beak
buff upperparts	buff breast	grey belly	black beak
brown underparts	grey throat	yellow belly	buff beak
grey underparts	yellow throat	black belly	blue crown
yellow underparts	black throat	white belly	brown crown
black underparts	white throat	buff belly	grey crown
white underparts	buff throat	rounded wings	yellow crown
buff underparts	black eye	pointed wings	black crown
solid breast	beak length about–	size small	white crown
striped breast	– the same as head	size medium	solid wing
multi-colored breast	beak length shorter–	very small size	spotted wing
brown back	– than head	duck-like	striped wing
grey back	blue forehead	perching-like	multi-colored wing
yellow back	brown forehead	solid back	
black back	grey forehead	striped back	

Shapes3d concept set

red floor	lime wall	purple object
orange floor	azure wall	pink object
yellow floor	blue wall	miniscule object
green floor	navy blue wall	very small object
lime floor	purple wall	small object
azure floor	pink wall	medium size object
blue floor	red object	slightly big object
navy blue floor	orange object	big object
purple floor	yellow object	very big object
pink floor	green object	enormous object
red wall	lime object	cube shaped object
orange wall	azure object	cylinder shaped object
yellow wall	blue object	sphere shaped object
green wall	navy blue object	pill shaped object

CelebA concept set

5 o Clock Shadow	Chubby	Pointy Nose
Arched Eyebrows	Double Chin	Receding Hairline
Attractive	Eyeglasses	Rosy Cheeks
Bags Under Eyes	Goatee	Sideburns
Bald	Gray Hair	Smiling
Bangs	Heavy Makeup	Straight Hair
Big Lips	High Cheekbone	Wavy Hair
Big Nose	Mouth Slightly Open	Wearing Earrings
Black Hair	Mustache	Wearing Hat
Blond Hair	Narrow Eyes	Wearing Lipstick
Blurry	No Beard	Wearing Necklace
Brown Hair	Oval Face	Wearing Necktie
Bushy Eyebrows	Pale Skin	Young

A.8 Concept Sets in other works

As a reference, we provide the number of concepts used in the original implementation of the methods we use in our experiments.

Table 10: Number of selected concepts for CUB dataset.

Model	N. Concepts CUB
CBM [41]	112
LF-CBM [58]	370
LaBo [80]	≥ 2000
VLG-CBM [72]	723

Appendix B Additional experimental results

Figure 4: Gaps in concept leakage test on Shapes3d dataset. Negative values indicate that the classifier using predicted concepts has lower F_1 score than the same which has access to ground-truth concept annotations.

B.1 Disentanglement

We provide in Fig. 6, Fig. 7, and Fig. 8 the DCI matrices obtained from the different models on Shapes3d, CelebA, and CUB, respectively.

Figure 5: Annotations obtained using G-DINO on the 3 different datasets. On CelebA (left) and Shapes3d (center) the VLM makes several mistakes highlighted by red crosses. On the other hand, the model does a good job annotating CUB (right).

Figure 6: **Importance matrices in DCI on Shapes3d.** High disentanglement is achieved when, for each row, only one square is active. For reference, a perfect DCI matrix is a diagonal matrix.

Figure 7: **Importance matrices in DCI on CelebA.** High disentanglement is achieved when, for each row, only one square is active. For reference, a perfect DCI matrix is a diagonal matrix.

Figure 8: **Importance matrices in DCI on CUB.** High disentanglement is achieved when, for each row, only one square is active. For reference, a perfect DCI matrix is a diagonal matrix.